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THE INVESTIGATION OF DESIGN FEATURES OF BRAINWAVES INDUCED BY COLORS.

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ABSTRACT

The display design of experience-oriented retail stores strongly affects consumers' emotions by lights, music, and colors. Colors can attract consumers' attention and influence their preferences, expectation, and decision-making toward the products. The present study is to investigate the effects of different color temperatures of store display on aesthetic brainwaves. We control the display color temperature at 6500K with matched colors red/green, yellow/red, and yellowish-green/green as the stimuli. Research findings showed that: (1) red/green combination induced greater aesthetic brainwave and attracted consumers' attention, aroused their emotions, interests, and desires more quickly, which contributed to the final buying behavior (action); (2) parietal lobe is a reliable area for observing color-induced brain responses. The results revealed that colors induced aesthetic brainwaves and activated brain regions situations. It is hoped that it will be beneficial for the color design in commercial application and cross-disciplinary development.

Keywords: color combination, memory, P300.

INTRODUCTION

The package colors of the products in the market can attract consumers' attention and influence the degree of their preferences and expectation, which contribute to buying behavior (Gstón & Rosires, 2010). Research has found that colors of objects help to define perception completely and adjust affective process related to trigger memories (Cano, Class, & Polich, 2009). Attention- and color-related brainwave research also indicated that detections of associated targets resulted in aesthetic brainwaves

(Polich, 2007; Wijers, Mulder, Okita, Mulder, & Scheffers, 1989). Moreover, aesthetic brainwaves play important roles in synesthesia in terms of early stage of perceptions, late stage of attention or during the inhibition process (Gebuis, Nijboer, & Van Der Smagt, 2009). The present study was conducted to understand the relationships between color combinations and aesthetic brainwaves. The purpose of the study is to: (1) understand the effects of different color combinations on aesthetic brainwaves; (2) to compare the relationships among different aesthetic brainwaves aroused by different color combinations. Also it takes aesthetic brainwaves as the index of changing attention, memory, and other psychological patterns to investigate the effects of different color combinations and to provide suggestions for application in commercial designs.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

AESTHETIC BRAINWAVES

When the stimulus detections connect with memory processing, it will activate P300 components (Polich, 2007), the positive potential between 300 and 1000 milliseconds. This wave is related to visual stimuli (Carretie, Iglesias, Garcia, & Ballesteros, 1997) and is produced for processing attention and memory (Polich, 2007). The typical scalp distribution of P300 is across the central electrode area (Fz, Cz, Pz), the amplitude gradually increases from frontal lobe to parietal lobe (Polich, 2007). P300 is active in the right parietal lobe cortex, which dominates visual spatial ability and is related to the target stimulus evaluation. Research results have revealed that the attention networks from frontal lobe to parietal lobe are broader in the right hemisphere than the left one. Therefore, compared with the left hemisphere or the central area, the

right hemisphere can activate larger P300 amplitude (Polich, 2007). When the brain processes tasks related to spatial locations, the interactive connection of information from right hemisphere to left hemisphere is stronger (Simon-Dack, et al., 2009). Inductive reasoning and other visual-related cognitive tasks are closely related to the right hemisphere, so the original waveform is lateralized to the right hemisphere (Chen, et al., 2007; Schmidt-Kassow, Schubotz, & Kotz, 2009).

P300 as one of the ERP components has been widely investigated, which related to attention, recognition, decision-making, memory and other cognitive abilities. It is the result of several brain areas working together, and is influenced by many factors like subjective probability, relevant tasks, the importance of stimuli, decision-making, the confidence of decision-making, uncertainty of stimuli, attention, memory, affections and so on (Chen, et al., 2007; Gilmore, Clementz, & Berg, 2009; Olofsson, Nordin, Sequeira, & Polich, 2008; Polich, 2007; Polich & Criado, 2006). When there are changes of stimuli, environment, the distribution of target attention, updates of the neural representation or memory, P300 will be aroused by the sensations (Polich, 2007) to construct the connection between attention and associative cortex storage (Chen, et al., 2007). The changes of stimuli attention and the need of basic memory processing affect the amplitude of P300. If the encoding of the stimuli successfully helps to store the memory which leads to the recovery of memory and cognition, the amplitude of P300 will increase (Polich, 2007). The present study defined P300 as the aesthetic brainwave to observe brain responses induced by colors.

METHODS

PARTICIPANTS

The participants of this study were 12 right-handed undergraduate and graduate students, whose ages were from 18 to 23 years old (21.16 on average), of college of design in one university of science and technology in Taiwan, including 4 males and 8 females. Every participant should pass the red-green color vision defects test to make sure that he/she does not have visual deficiencies or if his/her eyesight is above 0.8 after correction. Only who

passed the test can participate in the experiment. Forty-eight hours before the experiment, each participant stopped using stimuli such as caffeine, which will affects brainwaves, and avoided intense activities, in order to exclude other interference effects from brain wave records.

MATERIALS

According to the results of market observation, most convenience stores, supermarkets, and other retail stores display their products under 6500K color temperature lights (61.65%). These stores sell mainly juice, tea, water, energy drinks, soft drinks, coffee and so on, which were mostly in 1/3 (71.84%) aspect ratio round-shaped PET bottles. According to observation, the colors of the PET bottles are mainly matched by two visual base colors. Research has indicated that when two colors of the same square measure putting together, the harmony of colors perceived by people would be more consentient (Jhuang Ming Jhen & Ye Cing Lin, 1998). The present study was aimed to investigate two colors combination, so the experimental stimuli were designed in 1:1 square measure with up-down juxtaposition. The present study was based on the Munsell color wheel, the representative example of color appearance system, and considered the angles of two colors on the Munsell color wheel (Mahyar, Cheung, & Westland, 2010; Pridmore, 2008; Westland, Laycock, Cheung, Henry, & Mahyar, 2007; Uchita, 2008; Dí & Wang, 2009) to analyze the survey results of the color combinations of 360 PET and retort pouch samples in markets in Wan-Hua District of Taipei in Taiwan (see Note 1). Three categories applied most often in the markets served as the representatives of the stimuli: red/green (46.80%), yellow/red (13.92%), and yellowish-green/green (18.14%). Three color combinations in 80% of the bottle's square measure were put on three 1/3 aspect ratio round-shaped PET bottles respectively, and were collocated with white cap as the experimental stimuli of the present study.

Among all the physical factors in the illumination environment, light intensity and color temperature have the biggest and most direct effects on human bodies (Jiang Jhe Ming, Wang Wei, Liou Jian Jih, & Chen Jing Wun, 2007). The light intensity of most

convenience stores in Taiwan is above 1,000Lux, and between 1,000-3,000Lux in exhibit areas of supermarkets (Bureau of Standards, Metrology & Inspection, 1987). Therefore, the display color temperature was controlled in 6,500K, and the light intensity was set between the convenience stores and the exhibit areas of supermarkets as 2,000Lux. After choosing appropriate LED and white display background which was common in the convenience stores, the light box was customized to simulate situations for selling. In order to decrease other interference effects in the illumination environment, the experiment was conducted in a laboratory in which the lights were turned off. The experimental stimuli were designed as in Table 1.

Color combinations	red/green	yellow/red	yellowish-green/green
Munsell hue value /chroma	red 4.5R 4/13 green 4.5G 5/8	yellow 5Y 8/10 red 4.5R 4/13	yellowish-green 5GY 6/4 green 4.5G 5/8
Sample picture			
CIE L*a*b value	red L52*a75 *b57 green L29*a-21 *b16	yellow L82*a13 *b98 red L52*a75 *b57	yellowish-green L68*a-28*b67 green L29*a-21 *b16
number (percentage)	22 (46.80%)	11 (13.92%)	43 (18.14%)
Simulated sample picture			
Experimental situation Simulated picture			

Table 1. Experimental sample design

Before the experiment, participants briefly practiced to familiarize with the measurement of the brainwave experiment; during the experiment, every stimulus randomly appeared for 30 times, and the same kind of stimuli did not appear continuously. The total amount is 90 times. The experiment was conducted in a brainwave observation laboratory in the college of design of one university of science and technology in Taiwan. The experimental environment was strictly controlled to avoid interference effects such as noises, lights, room temperature and so on. The experimental light box was placed on a 70 cm

high table and was at a distance of 70-80 cm from the participant. The horizontal viewing angle was adjusted to 10-20.

The experiment recorded aesthetic brainwaves and the results were analyzed by the SPSS 12.0 statistic software through multivariate statistical analysis.

RESULTS

The aesthetic brainwave results, which were induced by experimental samples of color combination designs, were recorded from 12 electrodes and categorized the brain into 3 areas—"left hemisphere, central, and right hemisphere" and 4 areas—"frontal lobe, central, parietal lobe, and occipital lobe." The statistic analysis results of the aesthetic brainwave data and the brain areas are as follows (see Table 2).

The experimental samples of three color combinations have significant effects on "left, central, and right hemispheres" in terms of aesthetic brainwave amplitudes ($F = 4.835$, $P = 0.010 < 0.05$). The results of Tukey's HSD post hoc comparison showed that: the aesthetic brainwave amplitude induced by "red/green" combinations was greater than "yellowish-green/green" one. The interaction between experimental samples of three color combinations and "frontal lobe, central, parietal lobe, and occipital lobe" has significant effects on aesthetic brainwave amplitudes on average, multivariate test revealed that Wilks' Λ value was 0.508 ($P = 0.015 < 0.01$). The results of Tukey's HSD post hoc comparison indicated that in parietal lobe area, aesthetic brainwave amplitudes induced by "red/green" combination was greater than "yellowish-green/green" one; in occipital lobe area, aesthetic brainwave amplitude induced by "red/green" combination was greater than "yellow/red" or "yellowish-green/green" ones; in "red/green" combination, aesthetic brainwave amplitude in parietal lobe was greater than in occipital lobe and central brain, which was also greater than in frontal lobe; in "yellow-red" combination, aesthetic brainwave amplitude in parietal lobe was greater than in the occipital lobe and frontal lobe; in "yellowish-green/green" combination, aesthetic brainwave amplitude in parietal lobe was greater than in central brain,

Independent variables	Dependent Variables		Results				
	Brain areas	Aesthetic Brainwaves	Tukey's HSD (M)	ANOVA			
				F-value	P-value		
Color Combination	left, central, right brain	Aesthetic Brainwaves	Red/green (4.97) > yellowish-green/green (6.58)		4.835	0.010*	
	frontal, central, parietal, occipital		Frontal lobe : –	Under red/green : parietal (10.83) > occipital (8.36) , central (8.19) > frontal (5.76)		11.626	0.000***
			Central brain : –	Under Yellow/red : parietal (9.68) > occipital (6.80) , frontal (6.09)			
			Parietal : red/green (10.83) > yellowish-green/green (8.97)	Under Yellowish-green/green : parietal (8.97) > central (7.04) > frontal (5.00) ; parietal (8.97) > occipital (6.03)			
			Occipital : red/green (8.36) > yellow/red (6.80) , yellowish-green/green (6.03)				

Table 2. Results of the Independent variables

which was greater than in frontal lobe, and the aesthetic brainwave amplitude in parietal lobe was greater than in the occipital lobe.

Color-related brainwave research has indicated that brain can respond more quickly when there is greater contrast between the background color and the foreground color (Liu, Wang, Song, & Wu, 2010). Although the color application situations were different, the results of 3 simulated market situations in the present study coincided with the results of Liu, Wang, Song, & Wu (2010). The aesthetic brainwave amplitude is related to attention task efficiency that a greater amplitude is related to better cognitive memory performance (Boucher, et al., 2010). Compared the results of the aesthetic brainwave amplitudes induced by three color combinations samples, red/green combination caused greater amplitudes than yellowish-green/green one. Therefore, it was inferred that red/green combination can make the brain respond quicker, attract attention, complete attraction tasks, and have better cognitive memory performance.

In terms of color design, red and green, complementary colors in two ends of the color wheel's diameter, become the best color combination design which satisfied people's visual desires and needs because of the human eyes'

physiological characteristics. Besides, red/green and yellowish-green/green are also harmonious color combinations (Nagai & Uchikawa, 2009; Ou & Luo, 2006; Pridmore, 2008; Westland, et al., 2007). To sum up the discussion above, red/green combination can attract attention more quickly and have better cognitive memory performance, which can serve as a unique color combination design. Three physical channel color combination samples are shown in table 3.

Color combinations	red/green	yellow/red	yellowish-green/green
Pictures			

Table 3. Color combinations of physical channel samples

Observing three color combination samples, they all have significant effects on the aesthetic brainwaves in "frontal lobe, central, parietal lobe, and occipital lobe" areas. The amplitude in parietal lobe was greater than 3 other brain areas (see Figure 1). Research has pointed out that when participants changed or updated attention distribution on the targets or the stimulus environment changed, the aesthetic brainwave was induced by sensation and was positively and significantly related to the parietal lobe area (Polich, 2007).

Otherwise, the aesthetic brainwave was related to background updates of working memory, memory storage, and cognition control process (Fjell, et al., 2007; Gómez & Flores, 2011; Liu, et al., 2010; Polich, 2007). Therefore, red/green color combination can induce the greatest aesthetic brainwave amplitude, a design which connect sensory memory, retrieve and store memory more quickly.

Figure 1. Responses of the aesthetic brainwave amplitudes of 3 color combination samples

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DISCUSSION

Among 3 color combinations, red/green is a design which can catch attention, connect sensory memory and store memory more quickly. The present study used 3 color combinations in PET bottles as experimental samples to investigate the effects of color combinations on aesthetic brainwaves and the relationships between them. Liu, et al. (2010) investigated the effects of the colors of the traffic signs on brain cognition. The research found out that when the content of the traffic sign was easier and the contrast of the background and foreground colors were greater, the brain can respond more quickly. Cano, et al. (2009) applied negative, neutral, and positive pictures in International Affective Pictures System (IAPS) to investigate the relationship between colors and aesthetic brainwaves. The research indicated that object colors help to define sensation completely, and also help to adjust memory activation and other affective-related process. Furthermore, the research results which

used Stroop's test also pointed out that the aesthetic brainwave was related to better oral cognitive memory. The amount of the amplitude was related to the speed of color recognition process, the interference of attention index, and the shorter time to complete the task (Boucher, et al., 2010). Early brainwave research about color and attention has been searching for color-related target words to understand how the brain's cognition worked. The research suggested that there was a component, which was related to searching words in colors, occurred late and longer after the stimulus appeared. The relative detection of the targets would induce aesthetic brainwave components in the parietal lobe (Wijers, et al., 1989). Although the experimental stimuli and situations were different, the research also suggested that in brain cognition process and retail situation, color combinations had quite large effects on attention, target detection, situational information categorization and update, memory formation, and so on.

Red/green color combination induced greater amplitude in the right brain than the yellowish-green/green one. This result is similar with the previous research which indicated that the aesthetic brainwaves occurred in sensory-related right brain (Chen, et al., 2007; Polich, 2007; Simon-Dack, et al., 2009). Simon-Dack, et al., (2009) took dynamic laser light as stimulus to investigate the visual and tactile synesthesia. Chen, et al., (2007) pointed out that inductive reasoning and other visual-related cognitive tasks are closely related to the right hemisphere. Polich, J. (2007) found that when processing oddball task, which had various kinds of stimuli, the right hemisphere had the greater aesthetic brainwave amplitude than in the left or central one. The present study manipulated "color combination" designs as experimental stimuli also aroused greater aesthetic brainwave amplitudes in the right brain. Related research has indicated that right brain has more remarkable connections to keep attention, evaluate stimuli, detect targets, and update working memory/background information. Moreover, any thinking, decision-making and actions would require full utilization of memory database that contains the new and old, language, and non-language, emotion, and reason. (Cohen, 2007). In

addition, recent consumption research also verified that the AIDMA (Attention, Interest, Desire, Memory, Action) theory can apply to consumption situations and advertising copies (Cul, 2008; Imamura, Ogino, & Kato, 2009). Therefore, to summarize the above, it was inferred that red/green combination can catch consumers' attention more quickly, connect to sensory memory faster, produce designs with desires and memory, and contribute to the final buying action more easily.

CONCLUSION

The study results clearly discovered the following issues with regards to the presentation of colors, brainwave of aesthetics and activity in brain regions: (1) red/green combination induced greater aesthetic brainwave amplitudes; (2) the activation of the brain verified that parietal lobe was a reliable area to observe color, attention, and memory.

The aesthetic brainwaves play important roles in synesthesia in terms of early stage of perceptions, late stage of attention or during the inhibition process (Gebuis, et al., 2009). Recently, oddball studies which applied aural and visual stimuli have found that when the participants were anxious or depressed, the amplitudes of the aesthetic brainwaves in the parietal lobe would be lower (Campanella, et al., 2010). Therefore, it inferred that the red/green combination, which induced greater amplitudes, would have better attention, better cognitive memory performance, and arouse positive emotions more easily. The common impression of the red/green combinations such as merry Christmas, delicious fruits like tomatoes, watermelons and so on can easily arouse positive emotions. Colors play important roles in the brain's attention, emotions, memory and other cognitive process. The present study only took the most applied color combinations in the market: red/green (46.80%), yellow/red (13.92%), and yellowish-green/green (18.14%) combinations as the representations of stimuli. Therefore, it is suggested that the following research can base on the result of this study to further investigate the effects of other complementary, contrast, and similar color combinations on consuming emotions and consuming desires, then combined with brain cognitive

activities and behavior to construct more completed cross-disciplinary database of colors and consumers' emotional cognition and consuming behavior models. The present study designed PET bottle samples to investigate the effects of color combinations on the aesthetic brainwaves and was benefit for the future commercial colors application and cross-disciplinary research.

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[Note 1]

The present study was based on the hue angles of the main hues and other hues at the Munsell color wheel (Westland, Laycock, Cheung, Henry, & Mahyar, 2007; Chita, 2008; Di & Wang, 2009) to quantify two colors' included angle as 180, 150-120, and 90-30 three different levels. According to the The International Commission on Illumination (CIE), the types of the fluorescent light tube in the stores and the records of their color temperature when leaving the factory, the fluorescent light was quantified as three categories, high (7,500-5,000K), medium (3,300-5,000K), and low color temperature (below 3,300K). The present study took "the color temperature of white fluorescent light" and "hue angles" of color combinations to infer the market observational results (see Table 4).

Package Colors Number/Rank (%)		Color temperature of the white fluorescent light in the stores		
		High color temperature 7500-5000K 352/1 (61.65%)	Medium color temperature 3300-5000K 194/2 33.98%	Low color temperature below 3,300K 25/3 4.38%
Hue Angle	180° 78/3 (13.66%)	c 5/9 (0.87%)		
	150° - 120° 144/2 (25.21%)	f 9/8 (1.58%)		
	90° - 30° 349/1 (61.12%)	i 11/7 (1.93%)		

Table 4. The percentage of the color in the present study